

CMIP5 Climatology Data for the IPCC DDC

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Summary

CMIP5 monthly mean climatology fields matching those given in IPCC WG1 AR5 Annex I: Atlas of Global and Regional Climate Projections, for the global fields (Stoker et. al., 2013) have been calculated at CEDA. The climatologies calculated by CEDA match those described in table AI.1 in Stoker et al (2013) which describes the combination of models and experiments that were used in the construction of the Atlas.

Models, Experiments and Variables

An overview of the scope of the twenty- and thirty-year climatologies and climatological anomalies calculated by CEDA is captured in tables 1.1(list of models), 1.2 (list of experiments experiments) and 1.3 (list of variables).

Table 1.1 CMIP5 Models for which 20- and 30-year climatologies and climatological anomalies have been calculated.		
ACCESS1-0	FIO-ESM	inmcm4
ACCESS1-3	GFDL-CM3	IPSL-CM5A-LR
bcc-csm1-1	GFDL-ESM2G	IPSL-CM5A-MR
bcc-csm1-1-m	GFDL-ESM2M	IPSL-CM5B-LR
BNU-ESM	GISS-E2-H p1	MIROC5
CanESM2	GISS-E2-H p2	MIROC-ESM
CCSM4	GISS-E2-H p3	MIROC-ESM-CHEM
CESM1-BGC	GISS-E2-H-CC	MPI-ESM-LR
CESM1-CAM5	GISS-E2-R p1	MPI-ESM-MR
CMCC-CM	GISS-E2-R p2	MPI-ESM-P
CMCC-CMS	GISS-E2-R p3	MRI-CGCM3
CNRM-CM5	GISS-E2-R-CC	NorESM1-M
CSIRO-Mk3-6-0	HadGEM2-AO	NorESM1-ME

EC-EARTH	HadGEM2-CC	
FGOALS-g2	HadGEM2-ES	

Table 1.2
CMIP5 Experiments for which 20- and 30-year climatologies and climatological anomalies have been calculated.

Pre-Industrial Control (piControl)	RCP2.6 (rcp26)	RCP6.0 (rcp60)
20th Century (historical)	RCP4.5 (rcp45)	RCP8.5 (rcp85)
1% CO2 increase per year (1pctCO2)		

Table 1.3
CMIP5 Variables for which 20- and 30-year climatologies and climatological anomalies have been calculated.

specific_humidity (hus)	air_temperature (tas)	northward_wind (va)
precipitation_flux (pr)	air_temperature_max (tasmax)	eastward_wind_at_surface (uas)
air_pressure_at_sea_level (psl)	air_temperature_min (tasmin)	northward_wind_at_surface (vas)
surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air (rsds)	eastward_wind (ua)	specific_humidity_at_surface (huss)

Time periods

The climatological data for CMIP5 has been calculated with reference to 20- and 30-year period averages. The periods against which the climatologies are calculated are determined by the experiment to which the data is related.

Periods (20x and 30a) are defined as being:

- Relative to 2000 for future scenarios (RCPy.x)
- Relative to 1900 for 20th century (historical) experiment
- Relative to the beginning of the experiment for the piControl and 1pctCO2 experiments

The averaging periods covered are:

- 20x: Twenty year averages +20-30, +46-65, +80-99, +180-199
- 30a: Thirty year averages +01-30, +31-60, +61-90
- AR5: 2016-2035, 2046-2065, 2081-2100

Anomaly specification

All values are taken as anomalies from the 1986-2005 mean (baseline values).

For the Historical and RCP simulations these baseline values are taken from the 20th century experiment (historical). For the 1pctCO2 and piControl simulations the baseline values are taken from the last 20 years of the piControl experiment.

Output

- Period mean of the monthly mean of the variables
- 12 monthly values per climatology
- Climatology is a 2D field
- One climatology per model per scenario per variable per time period
- CF compliant netCDF files

Directory structure

The output directory structure follows the DRS specification (Taylor et. al. 2012) with the root directory being /derived/. Each file has the extended attribute: clim-anom-ref5. This indicates that it is a climatological mean anomaly (clim-anom) and that the reference period matches the AR5 reference period (ref 5).

Method

The algorithm for calculating the baseline climatologies and climatological anomalies follows the process below:

- For every model:
 - For every variable (if available):
 - calculate the 1986-2005 climatological (period average) monthly means (baseline) for the Historical experiment
- For every model:
 - For every variable (if available):
 - calculate the period average monthly means (baseline) of the last 20 years of the piControl run
- For every model:
 - For every experiment:
 - For every time period:
 - For every variable (if available):
 - calculate the climatological monthly mean for this (model, experiment, time period, variable) and subtract the relevant baseline

Code

The code for calculating the climatological baselines and anomalies can be found in the CEDA github repository https://github.com/cedadev/ipcc_ddc_cmip5_clim_anoms
Program: Common functions for calculating climatologies of CMIP5 models for upload to the IPCC Data Distribution Centre.
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References

Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.) (2013), IPCC, 2013: *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp, doi:10.1017/CBO9781107415324.

Taylor, Karl E and Balaji, V and Hankin, Steve and Juckes, Martin and Lawrence, Bryan and Pascoe, Stephen (2012), CMIP5 data reference syntax (DRS) and controlled vocabularies, http://cmip-pcmdi.llnl.gov/cmip5/docs/cmip5_data_reference_syntax.pdf